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The Export Restraints Policy: The Reverse Protectionism on the International Trade

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Abstract

Currently, several lawsuits have been established into the World Trade Organization (WTO) dispute settlement body related with the use of some trade policies where countries block their exports abroad as a sort of protectionism which is not entirely regulated by the multilateral trading system. Therefore, this scenario is pushing states to sign particular commitments on the accession protocol of the WTO in order to be new members, besides to develop parallels legal frameworks through Free Trade Agreements (FTA) that undermine the current legal system. All these differences usually cite articles from the General Agreement and Tariffs on Trade (GATT) and others legal texts, therefore, the multilateral trading system requires to perform a new round of negotiations for adjusting some obsoletes rules, especially when considering the increase of the "reverse protectionism" due to the depletion of natural resources which leads to new challenges for international relations.

Keywords: Export restraints, reverse protectionism, multilateral trading system, GATT, WTO

Introduction

The emergence of the GATT in 1947 established a legal agreement to promote international trade among their contracting states by reducing or eliminating unjustified protectionist policies such as tariff barriers (TB), and non-tariff barriers (NTB) (Rohlfing-Dijoux, 2017). Thus, the GATT's purpose was the substantial reduction of tariffs and other trade barriers and the elimination of preferences, on a reciprocal and mutually advantageous basis.

Later, after eight rounds of multilateral trade negotiations, the GATT was updated in 1994 to include new obligations upon its signatories taking into account new arrangements on goods, services, intellectual property, dispute settlement, trade policy review mechanisms, and the plurilateral agreements known as "legal texts"; and all these new arrangements allowed the creation of the WTO in 1995 which currently counts with 164 member countries. In this sense, it was also developed the dispute settlement body (DSB) which serves to manage the disputes among members and is vital for the observance of the regulations in order to make possible the flow of commercial exchange between countries through a clear legal framework (Marceau, 2015; WTO, 2018b).

Consequently, the DSB has witnessed the rise of new disputes related to trade policies, where WTO member countries adopt export restraints related to national security due to environmental or economic purposes. For instance, some export restraints aim to guarantee food security and stabilization of market prices or aim to promote domestic industries providing raw materials and cheap supplies (Jeonghoi, 2010).

Therefore, this article shows the disputes currently existing related to the reverse protectionism, the restrictions applied to the exports, the countries using this type of mechanisms, the WTO members with

protocols of accession where it is prohibited the implementation of export restraints, and some relevant FTA on international trade that prohibits the export restraints on their texts.

The Multilateral Trading System and the Export Restraints

According to Pierola (2007), since the establishment of GATT in 1947 eight rounds of negotiation were carried out for almost five decades within this initiative until the creation of the WTO in 1995. Thus, all this have been the key to create common policies and normative provisions for the countries into the international trade. Different topics were discussed in these meetings and were made by the same contracting parties of GATT, providing some rules and including the legal texts to regulate and to correct inefficiencies and facilitating trade flows that for many years lacked a real legal order.

Thus, the international trading system configuration has been a quite complicated process due to the countries have had to negotiate diverse issues in most of those rounds ever since and even today, as shown in Table 1. These rounds of negotiation considered some topics related to the role of TB, which at the same time were the central theme covered in the GATT's agenda, besides other topics like the NTB, regulations, services, intellectual property, dispute settlements, textiles, agriculture, among others (Howse, 1998; Baena & Fernández, 2016).

Table 1: The rounds of negotiation within the GATT and the rounds of negotiation within WTO

Year	Denomination	Participating countries	Issues addressed
1947	Geneva (GATT)	23	TB
1949	Annecy (GATT)	13	TB
1951	Torquay (GATT)	38	TB
1956	Geneva (GATT)	26	TB
1960 - 1961	Geneva - Dillon Round (GATT)	26	TB
1964 - 1967	Geneva - Kennedy Round (GATT)	62	TB and anti-dumping measures
1973 - 1979	Geneva - Tokyo Round (GATT)	102	TB, NTB and agreements related to the legal framework.
1986 - 1994	Geneva - Uruguay Round (GATT)	123	TB, NTB, regulations, services, intellectual property, dispute settlement, textiles, agriculture, the creation of the WTO, among others.
2001	Doha Round (WTO)	157	Agriculture, services, access to markets for non-agricultural products, intellectual right property aspects related with trade, relationship between trade and investments, interaction between trade and competition policy, transparency in government procurement, trade facilitation, anti-dumping, subsidies, regional trade agreements, dispute settlement understanding, trade and environment, recently acceded members, help for trade, special and differential treatment, among others.

Source: Based on WTO (2017) and Silva (2001).

According to Lal-Das (2004), the functioning of the current multilateral trading system depends on the confidence among the member countries, in fact, it is essential that the full members of the WTO perceive confidence in an atmosphere of reciprocity that benefit them. Indeed, this is the most important aspect for their basic structure allowing to develop regulations which increase the participation of the members in the decision-making. However, nowadays it is perceived an unbalance regulation in the same decision-making that eventually need to be overcome after the Doha Round failure (Khor, 2003).

Baldwin (2016) affirms that most of the objectives of the multilateral trading system have been achieved, making it possible to consolidate the WTO as a trade paradigm based on regulations universally accepted and respected among all of its members. It has also been possible that the TB have decreased in historical average levels despite the Doha Round, which has experienced severe setbacks and failures since its launching in 2001.

Although Baena et al. (2017) affirm that the NTB have increased regarding the TB, the current protectionism is currently led by the NTB because the old GATT regime and the WTO have been focusing the negotiations rounds on the TB without developing solid provisions related with the adoption of these trade policies. Another critical issue within the WTO is related with the under-regulation for exports restraints, where countries develop trade policies implementing TB or NTB in order to restrict the exit of goods and guarantee particular interests to preserve national security objectives of a state (Bernitz & Ringe, 2010).

Thus, there is remarkable deficiency in the current legal framework given that TB and NTB for exports seem not to be adequately regulated by the WTO which has led to special situations where the new members in the WTO must sign clauses on their protocols of accession that include the prohibition of export restraints (Korinek & Bartos, 2012). Likewise, the states signing free FTA are including clauses where members prohibit the use of export restraints (Mildner & Lauster, 2011), leading to parallel international trade policies and undermining the rules of the multilateral trading system contained in the GATT's provisions and the legal texts managed by the WTO (Baena, 2016; Baena & Cano, 2018).

Why Countries Adopt TB And NTB to Restrain their Exports?

According to Mildner and Lauster (2011), the export restrictions have been implemented due to different reasons that meet to political goals such as national security and environmental protection, social goals, among others. However, as shown in Table 2, this type of trade policy meets to economic goals such as the increase in public incomes, the promotion of downstream industries, the diversification of exports, and the control of fluctuations on prices, among others.

Table 2: Economic reasons motivating the use of TB and NTB in exports

Type	Measure	Reasons
TB	Improvement in the terms of trade	When restricting the exports, a country that provides an important world market share may elevate its world price. This implies an improvement in its terms of trade, which allows the importing country to pay more per unit of the exported goods.
	Food security and stabilization of the final price of consumption	When creating a gap between the world price and the internal price, exports taxes reduce the exports to redirect the goods offer towards the internal market. For example, the government of Indonesia imposes taxes to the export of palm oil products, including crude oil and cooking palm oil in 1994, due to the cooking oil is considered as an essential product. During the food crisis of 2006-2008, this was the main reason for several governments to apply taxes and other restrictions for exports.
	Stabilization of intermediate prices of consumption and development of processing industries	The taxes to the export of primary products (especially unprocessed products) work as a subsidy for most of the value-added processing industries because this measure promotes the supply and the reduction of internal prices in the supplies in comparison with the world price.
	Increase in public incomes	The taxes for exports provide incomes to the developing countries, mainly when there is a limited capacity to depend on the internal taxation.
	Redistribution of income	As with the imports charges, the exports tariffs imply the redistribution of the incomes. The exports taxes affect national producers and favor national consumers and public incomes, whereas the imports tariffs affect domestic consumers, but favor national producers and public incomes.
	Stabilization of the export earnings	In order to stabilize internal prices and export income for exporters, some developing countries apply high tax rates when the export prices are higher than the prices of the national products, or low taxes on the contrary case.
NTB	Protecting and promoting national transforming and/or processing industries with raw materials and cheap supplies	This policy leads to the same result using both NTB and TB because both measures are categorized as export restrictions. Thus, both the quantitative restrictions and the rights to export provide an important advantage for the processing industries that use raw materials to make finished goods.
	Promoting social policies such as environmental protection or conservation of natural resources	This is the most popular objective to justify a quantitative restriction on exports or even a safeguarding. Limiting the trade volume of certain resources is a key factor and to a lesser extent, the export duties are also used to achieve these political objectives.
	Controlling the inflationary pressures and assuring the	An increase in the international price of a product may create inflationary pressures, thus, the NTB may act as a measure to control inflation, maintaining stable prices of

	internal supply (especially for agricultural products for food safety)	the basic products. An export restriction promotes an increase in the internal offer, reduces the internal price of the product and compensates partially the inflationary pressures coming from the highest prices abroad.
	Countering the tariff escalation	The export restrictions may counter the tariff progressivity of the importing countries. This practice consists of collecting higher import TB for elaborated products compared with those unprocessed. The use of export taxes was suggested by several countries as a political option to reduce the impact on the tariff progressiveness on their exports of processed products.

Source: Based on Bouet and Laborde (2010)

Thus, according to Baena and Cano (2018), the reverse protectionism for exports seems to be more popular and they are increasingly included in new trade agreements, showing some problems in the multilateral trading system related with the export restraints. Therefore, this type of trade policies tends to be relatively recent given that the restrictions to the export of goods were not regulated by the GATT due to the low application by the countries in the international trade (Lambert & Rueffer, 2010).

Consequently, the export restrictions are not still emphasized within the multilateral trading system, at least in legal terms, despite this issue takes more importance within the international trade. The reverse protectionist policies usually respond to phenomena that may be related with the monopolization of resources by certain groups of interest and to the configuration of economic cartels due to the increasing scarcity produced by the depletion of resources (Matsushita, 2011; Bolotova, 2009).

Methodology

In order to contextualize the reverse protectionism, and to identify the main disputes within the DSB in the WTO, a theoretical framework has been created based on high impact scientific databases such as Web of Science (WOS), Scopus, Science Direct, Ebsco, Doaj, and Scielo, using search criteria corresponding to export restrictions, multilateral trading system, GATT, and WTO.

Consequently, the WTO official website was consulted, especially in the sections of “Chronological list of Disputes Cases” and “Accession Commitments Database” to identify the differences related with export restraints such as TB and NTB into the multilateral trading system, and to recognize new members of the WTO which signed especial commitments related with the non-imposition of export restraints. Besides, we consulted some ministries of trade and industry in order to find FTAs, facilitating the access to reliable secondary sources to find essential data which allowed to explain and describe the reverse protectionism.

Results and Discussion

Table 3 shows the disputes reported chronologically to the DSB related to export restraints such as TB or NTB since the origins of the multilateral trading system with the former regime of the GATT and current regime of the WTO. During the former regime of the GATT 101 disputes were reported until the end of the Uruguay Round, while in the current WTO it has been reported 566 disputes. It is possible to remark that during the former regime of the GATT all these disputes were related with measures where countries adopted NTB as export restraints, and then during the current the WTO some of them were also related with NTB. Therefore, 46.7% of disputes presented to the DSB in the multilateral trading system have to do with NTB measures, while the remaining 53.3% of measures are related to TB, whereby TB are currently the most common measures for export restraints.

Table 3: Current disputes in the multilateral trading system

N°	Regime	Respondent country	Product	Laws invoked	Complainant country	Dispute name	Type of measure	
1	Former regime of the GATT	United States	General goods	Articles I and XXI (GATT)	Czechoslovakia	BISDII/28 (1949)	NTB	
2		Canada	Herring and Salmon, unprocessed	Articles XI and XX (GATT)	United States	BISD35S/98 (1986)		
3		European Economic Commission	Waste of copper	Articles XI (GATT)	United States	BISD37S/200 (1990)		
4	Current regimen of the WTO	Pakistan	Leather and fur	Articles XI and XXIII (GATT)	European Communities	DS107 (1997)	NTB	
5		India				DS120 (1998)		
6		Argentina				Articles X and XI (GATT)		DS155 (1998)
7		United States	General goods	Agreement on Agreement on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures (ASCM) Articles 1, 10, 11, 17, 19 and 32. Articles XVI: 4 Marrakesh Agreement	Canada	DS194 (2000)		
8		China	Rare earth elements	Articles VII, VIII, X and XI (GATT). Accession Protocol.	United States	DS394 (2009)		TB
9						DS431 (2012)		
10	European Communities					DS395 (2009)		
11	DS432 (2012)							
12	Mexico					DS398 (2009)		
13	Japan					DS433 (2012)		
14	United States					DS508 (2016)		
15	Raw materials	Articles X and XI. Accession Protocol.	European Union	DS509 (2016)				

Source: Based on (WTO, 2018c)

On the other hand, Table 4 shows an example of eight (8) countries as new members in the WTO that have signed special clauses on their accession protocol, proving the development of new parallel legal systems because founder members of the WTO did not sign specific commitment to become members.

Table 4: New members in the WTO with special clauses on their accession protocol

Date of Accession	Country	Commitments
1-Dec-96	Bulgaria	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices -038 039 (TB)
		Quantitative import restrictions, including prohibitions, quotas, and licensing systems - 047 (NTB)
8-Sept-00	Albania	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices - 087 (TB)
		Technical barriers to trade - 095 (NTB)
30-Nov-00	Croatia	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices -100 (TB)
		Export restrictions - 102 (NTB)
11-Dec-01	China	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices -155 (TB)
		Export restrictions - 157 (NTB)
5-Feb-03	Armenia	Export restrictions - 107 (NTB)
		Trade Agreements - 205 (TB)

13-Oct-04	Cambodia	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices - 109 (TB)
		Export restrictions -112 (NTB)
23-Jul-08	Cabo Verde	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices - 145 (TB)
		Export restrictions - 146 (NTB)
29-Jul-16	Afghanistan	Customs tariffs, fees, and charges for services rendered, application of internal taxes to exports and minimum export prices -143 (TB)
		Export restrictions -146 (NTB)

Source: Based on WTO (2018d)

After the creation of the WTO many different countries have tried to become full members of this international organization, however, these countries have experienced many lengthy negotiation processes to achieve this goal. Then, 36 new members have signed special commitments related to export restraints for TB and NTB with respect to founder countries 23 years ago. Table 5 shows an example of ten (10) normative provisions signed for FTA where their members agreed to develop parallels legal frameworks. Therefore, after to access to the WTO regional trade agreement database it was possible to prove that countries are signing FTA, incorporating special clauses to regulate export restraints.

Table 5: Some FTA with normative provisions related to export restraints

Date of entry into force	FTA	Rule developed - Article	Source
01-Jan-2004	United States - Singapore	2.4 Export Tax (TB) 2.7 Import and export restrictions (NTB)	(USTR, 2004)
01-Jun-2005	Turkey - Palestinian Authority	12 Customs Duties on Imports or Exports and Charges Having Equivalent Effect (TB) 13 Quantitative Restrictions on Imports or Exports and Measures having Equivalent Effect	(WTO, 2005)
01-Dec-2008	ASEAN - Japan	17 Customs Valuation 18 Non-tariff Measures	(MOFA, 2008)
01-Feb-2009	United States - Peru	2.8 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB) 2.11 Export Taxes (TB)	(USTR, 2009)
08-May-2009	Chile - Colombia	3.2 Export Taxes (TB) 3.4 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB)	(DIRECON, 2009)
15-Aug-2011	Canada - Colombia	207 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB) 210 Export Taxes (TB)	(GAC, 2011)
15-May-2012	United States - Colombia	2.8 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB) 2.11 Export Taxes (TB)	(USTR, 2011)
01-Oct-2012	EFTA - Hong Kong, China	2.3 Elimination of Customs Duties (TB) 2.4 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB)	(EFTA, 2012)
01-Mar-2013	EU - Colombia and Peru	23 Import and Export Restrictions (NTB) 25 Duties and Taxes on Exports (TB)	(EUR-Lex, 2013)
20-Dec-2015	Australia - China	2.6 Customs Valuation (TB) 2.7 Non-Tariff Measures (NTB)	(DFAT, 2015)

Source: Based on WTO (2018a)

Having reviewed all the special commitments related with export restraints for TB and NTB, it is possible to detect that all these FTA have implemented articles related to export restraints on their constitutive texts. Likewise, most of them seem to adopt almost the same idea and rule; in the first case it is established for TB “[...] except as otherwise provided in this Agreement, no Party may adopt or maintain any prohibition or restriction on the importation of any good of another Party or on the

exportation or sale for export of any good destined for the territory of another Party”. For the second case it is established for NTB “[...] except as otherwise provided in this Agreement, no Party may adopt or maintain any duty, tax, or other charge on the export of any good to the territory of another Party, unless the duty, tax, or charge is also adopted or maintained on the good when destined for domestic consumption”. In this sense, the current FTA carried out in the multilateral trading system are adopting rules for export restraint complementing the provisions of GATT and legal texts.

Conclusions

This research proves how the reverse protectionism begins to have relevance into the multilateral trading system not only because of the constant appearance of new cases in the DSB but also because of the incapability of the WTO for regulating this issue. Then, this has driven to different countries to sign FTA with particular clauses connected to export restraints.

The reverse protectionism for export restraints seems to increase due to the depletion of natural resources besides new policy trends associated with national security interests. Therefore, this leads the multilateral trading system facing new challenges for keeping the stability of the international relations.

Finally, there is a clear evidence of the need to conduct a round of negotiation in the multilateral trading system where the reverse protectionism must be fully addressed to develop new trade policies that regulate this issue.

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